

Table 3. The pharmacokinetic properties of SAHA and the target compounds 2A-E.

Parameter	Compound					
	SAHA	2A	2B	2C	2D	2E
Passive GI absorption	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
BBB permeability	Yes	No	No	No	No	No
P-gp substrate	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
CYP1A2 inhibitor	No	No	No	No	No	No
CYP2C19 inhibitor	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
CYP2C9 inhibitor	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
CYP2D6 inhibitor	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
CYP3A4 inhibitor	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Log K_p (skin permeation) cm/s	-6.23	-6.79	-7.15	-7.31	-6.75	-6.43